

Uncertainty-aware hydrological predictions in the Upper Adige river basin (Eastern Italian Alps, Italy)

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1. Case study overview

The Upper Adige River Basin, located in the eastern Italian Alps, is characterized by strong elevation gradients, complex hydrological processes, and a growing vulnerability to both floods and droughts. Water-resource management in the basin relies on timely and reliable streamflow predictions to support five core operations: (i) flood warning and civil protection, (ii) reservoir operations, (iii) hydropower production, (iv) irrigation planning, and (v) drought mitigation. However, traditional hydrological forecasts are affected by compounding sources of uncertainty, including errors in meteorological forcing data, structural model limitations, parameter estimation challenges, and the representation of snow and glacier melt processes. Quantifying these uncertainties is therefore essential to transform raw data into robust operational decisions.

To address this key challenge, the Autonomous Province of Bolzano (Italy) has developed two distinct operational hydrological forecasting frameworks, one operating in real-time and the other on a seasonal scale, for the entire Upper Adige River Basin. The resulting forecasting information is explicitly tailored for water managers, civil protection authorities and reservoir operators responsible for regional flood risk reduction and water allocation. In this context, uncertainty-aware hydrological predictions provide not only a standard best-estimate forecast but also a quantitative assessment of forecast confidence, enabling decision-makers to evaluate the likelihood of critical flow conditions and to adopt proactive, uncertainty-informed management strategies during both flood and drought events.

While these operational real-time and seasonal frameworks target immediate and medium-term tactical tasks, estimating predictive uncertainty in a continuous simulation-mode environment (where the hydrological model is driven by observed historical

meteorological data; Klemeš 1986) remains equally essential. Indeed, this continuous setup is necessary for evaluating long-term model reliability, diagnostic benchmarking and uncertainty-informed water resources management. To fulfill this need, a recent development has coupled traditional hydrological modelling with semi-parametric statistical post-processing. By conditioning observed streamflow on hydrological model outputs in this way, we avoid rigid parametric assumptions regarding the conditional distribution and deliver predictive uncertainty estimates of streamflow without requiring modifications to the core hydrological model or its calibration.

2. Study area, data and methods

2.1 Study area and hydro-climatic setting

The Upper Adige River Basin (approximately 6,900 km²) is located in the eastern Italian Alps and forms the headwaters of the Adige River, one of the largest river systems in Italy. The basin is characterized by highly complex alpine terrain, featuring severe topographic gradients with elevations shifting from valley floors below 300 m a.s.l. to mountain peaks exceeding 3,900 m a.s.l. (Norbiato et al. 2008). These strong topographic gradients exert a major control on precipitation patterns, snow accumulation, temperature, and runoff generation processes. The region experiences a humid alpine climate, with annual precipitation generally ranging from 600 to over 1,600 mm, depending largely on elevation and exposure to prevailing atmospheric circulation patterns.

Hydrological processes within the basin are influenced by the complex interaction of rainfall, seasonal snow accumulation and melt, glacier contributions in the highest elevations, and substantial geological heterogeneity. The complex geological setting comprises both low-permeability metamorphic formations and highly permeable carbonate and dolomitic rocks, leading to marked spatial variability in groundwater storage and runoff response. These characteristics result in diverse hydrological regimes, ranging from flashy flood responses in steep alpine catchments to delayed runoff generation in areas with significant groundwater storage. The basin plays a strategic role in water resources management, supporting hydropower production, irrigation, ecosystem services, and flood-risk management throughout northern Italy.

2.2 Datasets and temporal resolution

The historical datasets include precipitation (61 stations), air temperature (61 stations) and streamflow (45 stations) measurements collected at an hourly temporal resolution. Observational records span approximately 25–40 years, covering the period from the late 1980s through 2025. Precipitation data are corrected for snowfall undercatch, and temperature observations are used to distinguish rainfall from snowfall and to support snowmelt estimation. Streamflow records are obtained from gauging stations located on largely natural river systems, providing a consistent basis for hydrological modelling and uncertainty assessment.

Beyond historical observations, meteorological forecast data tailored to two distinct prediction horizons are integrated into the frameworks. For short-term real-time forecasting, high-resolution, short-range numerical weather prediction ensembles are used, consisting of a 22-member ensemble of precipitation and temperature forecasts (21 perturbed members and one deterministic control). These are available at a 2.2 km spatial resolution and the hourly temporal resolution, spanning a 3-day horizon from the forecast initialization time (“now”). For medium-to-long-range, seasonal forecasting, dynamical seasonal forecasts, sourced from the ECMWF seasonal ensemble prediction system via the Copernicus Climate Change Service, are deployed.

2.3 Hydrological model, calibration and validation

In previous and ongoing research (e.g., Shrestha et al. 2025) and operational activities, hydrological simulations are carried out using a semi-distributed, continuous rainfall-runoff model developed for operational forecasting in the Upper Adige River Basin (Norbiato et al. 2008, 2009; Zaramella et al. 2019). The model represents the main components of the hydrological cycle, including precipitation partitioning into rainfall and snowfall, snow accumulation and melt, evapotranspiration, soil moisture dynamics, runoff generation, and flow routing. Soil moisture accounting is based on the probability distributed moisture framework, which represents the spatial variability of soil water storage capacity through a probability distribution and simulates runoff generation as a function of catchment wetness conditions. Snow accumulation and melt are represented through a temperature-index approach, while potential evapotranspiration is estimated from meteorological observations. Direct runoff and baseflow are routed through fast and slow linear reservoirs, respectively, with response times derived from geomorphological

characteristics extracted from a digital elevation model. Flow routing along the river network and between sub-basins is performed using the Muskingum–Cunge method. Operating at an hourly time step, this model setup is fully integrated into daily operational workflows for both flood forecasting and water resources management.

Within the ongoing operational framework, model calibration has been carried out using hourly observations of precipitation, temperature, and streamflow collected over more than 30 alpine catchments within the basin. Model parameters have been estimated through a combination of automatic optimization and manual adjustment, with particular attention to reproducing both flood peaks and low-flow conditions. The overall model performance was rigorously evaluated using split-sample calibration and validation procedures, yielding Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (Nash and Sutcliffe 1970) values generally in the range of 0.65–0.75 alongside low volume bias, demonstrating satisfactory skill in reproducing the hydrological response across a wide range of hydro-climatic conditions.

2.4 Ensemble-based uncertainty estimation

Within the short-term, real-time forecasting framework, ensemble-based uncertainty is estimated by propagating the 22-member meteorological ensemble described in [Section 2.2](#) through the continuous hydrological model. Each ensemble member results in a distinct streamflow simulation over the 3-day operational window. The spread among the 22 simulated hydrographs provides a direct estimate of forecast uncertainty arising from meteorological inputs, allowing the system to represent a range of plausible hydrological responses rather than a single deterministic prediction.

Two seasonal ensemble-based methodologies are also employed. The ensemble streamflow prediction method is a widely used hydrological forecasting approach that exploits the knowledge of current catchment conditions, including soil moisture, groundwater storage, and snowpack. These initial conditions are propagated through a hydrological model using all available historical meteorological sequences, generating an ensemble of plausible future streamflow scenarios. In contrast, the ECMWF forecasts are driven by meteorological predictions from the ECMWF seasonal ensemble prediction system (51 members) and therefore incorporate information on the expected future atmospheric conditions.

2.5 Predictive uncertainty estimation

Predictive uncertainty is estimated using the linear-in-parameters quantile regression (Koenker and Bassett 1978) as a hydrological post-processor (Papacharalampous and Tyralis 2022). Specifically, the post-processor conditions the predictive quantiles of the streamflow distribution at the levels $\tau \in \{0.025, 0.10, 0.50, 0.90, 0.975\}$ upon the hydrological model outputs. In quantile regression, the parameters of the linear model, a and b , are optimized separately for each quantile level by minimizing the pinball loss function (e.g., Gneiting 2011, Eq. 24), an asymmetric loss function that relies on weighted error sums. This modelling approach collectively estimates all underlying sources of predictive uncertainty (input, model and parameter), yielding an approximation of the conditional distribution of streamflow (comprising the predictive median, 80% central prediction intervals and 95% central prediction intervals) at each time point at the hourly timescale. The training and testing of the hydrological post-processor are conducted using time periods that are independent of each other and have not been used for calibrating the core hydrological model. The absolute predictive performance is assessed using the quantile identification function (e.g., Gneiting 2011, Table 9), which should approximate zero for the predictions to be reliable.

3. Results

3.1 Ensemble-based uncertainty estimation

For each forecast point, the protocol (see Figure 1) presents both the deterministic simulation and the ensemble spread. The tables report precipitation as rain and snow, snow water equivalent, maximum forecast discharge, maximum water level, and timing of the peak. Importantly, the ensemble is summarized using minimum, 25th percentile, median, 75th percentile, and maximum values. For example, at Aurino, the +3 day forecast shows a deterministic peak discharge of about 70 m³/s, while the ensemble range extends from about 35 m³/s to 115 m³/s, with the upper ensemble member reaching the warning threshold range.

Figure 1. Example of the operational ensemble-based hydrological forecasting window generated by the Autonomous Province of Bolzano, for the Aurino river basin. The resulting probabilistic forecasts (summarized by the minimum, 25th percentile, median, 75th percentile and maximum values) are evaluated against localized critical warning thresholds to support risk-based operational decision-making.

From a flood forecasting perspective, this is valuable because the forecast is not presented as a single hydrograph only. The ensemble members provide a practical estimate of predictive uncertainty, mainly reflecting uncertainty in meteorological forcing and its hydrological propagation through snow accumulation/melt, rainfall-runoff response, and river routing. The envelope between the lower and upper ensemble members indicates how much confidence the forecaster should place in the predicted peak magnitude and timing.

This information can strongly support decision making. If only the deterministic forecast remains below a warning threshold, but the upper ensemble members exceed it, the civil protection operator may decide to increase monitoring, pre-alert local authorities, check vulnerable river reaches, or prepare field crews without yet issuing a full alarm. Conversely, if both the deterministic forecast and most ensemble members remain below thresholds, the response can be more proportionate. In other words, the ensemble helps shift operational flood management from a yes/no deterministic decision

toward a risk-based decision, where actions are calibrated according to both expected severity and forecast uncertainty.

Figure 2 presents the seasonal streamflow forecast for the Adige River at Bronzolo issued on June 1, 2026, comparing the historical climatological distribution (orange) with forecasts derived from the ensemble streamflow prediction (blue) and the ECMWF seasonal ensemble prediction system (green). For each lead time (10–90 days), boxplots summarize the ensemble distribution in terms of minimum, 25th percentile, median, 75th percentile, and maximum discharge.

Figure 2. Examples of seasonal ensemble-based hydrological forecasts generated by the Autonomous Province of Bolzano, for the Adige - Bronzolo river basin. The resulting probabilistic forecasts are summarized by the minimum, 25th percentile, median, 75th percentile and maximum values.

Both forecasting systems indicate flows consistently below climatological conditions throughout the forecast horizon. The median discharges predicted by the ensemble streamflow prediction and ECMWF ensembles are systematically lower than the climatological median and often approach or fall below the climatological lower quartile. The two forecasting approaches provide remarkably consistent results despite relying on different sources of predictive information, indicating the impact of the initial

conditions on these forecasts. Ensemble spread is generally smaller for the ECMWF-based forecasts than for climatology, suggesting a relatively coherent forecast signal. Overall, the figure indicates a persistent tendency toward below-average discharge conditions over the coming three months, with no clear indication of recovery toward normal seasonal flows.

3.2 Predictive uncertainty estimation

[Figure 3](#) displays examples of predictive uncertainty estimates issued with the hydrological post-processing framework for the Ridanna river basin. For this basin, the post-processor was trained and tested using 21 years of hourly data. Its reliability is confirmed by identification functions that closely approximate zero for the independent testing period. Furthermore, the same figure shows the post-processor's effectiveness in correcting model biases, particularly during low-flow conditions.

Figure 3. Examples of predictive uncertainty estimates in the test period for the Rio Ridanna at Vipiteno compared with observed and simulated streamflow.

4. Discussion

4.1 Technical successes

The implementation demonstrates that complementary, uncertainty-aware frameworks relying on a single core hydrological model can be deployed to address a broad spectrum of operational decisions and regional water resources management tasks at scale with minimal computational requirements. This integrated setup effectively pairs short-term real-time alerting and medium-term seasonal forecasting capabilities to support both immediate tactical interventions and long-term water resource scheduling. Parallel

to these components, the semi-parametric hydrological post-processing framework for predictive uncertainty estimation in simulation mode provides integrated bias correction while allowing long-term diagnostic benchmarking for the core hydrological model.

4.2 Technical difficulties

The main technical challenges experienced were related to heterogeneous programming environments and software language integration. Based on this knowledge, when we designed the simulation-mode framework, we selected a standalone hydrological post-processor that bypasses such challenges. Indeed, as this is running independently from the core hydrological model, diverse programming tools can effectively coexist without requiring code adaptation. Moreover, the system faced difficulties related to high-volume data transmission across different institutions and organizational networks.

4.3 Uncertainty communication lessons

Several key lessons were learned regarding uncertainty communication, starting with the fundamental principle that uncertainty estimates, especially in real-time, operational forecasting, should be automatically mapped onto localized operational thresholds. More generally, operationalizing uncertainty estimation requires translating complex technical frameworks into accessible, actionable insights while maintaining scientific rigor and accuracy.

A critical takeaway is the importance of understanding how uncertainty directly affects the timing and strength of operational decisions. For instance, when a flood alert carries high uncertainty, a civil protection operator may choose to wait "one night more" to gather additional data. This cautious approach helps avoid costly, highly disruptive false alerts, such as initiating a village evacuation based on insufficient evidence, while ensuring that the measures deployed remain proportionate to the risk. This dynamic highlights the need to align different visions of risk and responsibility between scientists and decision-makers. For a scientist, a 1% probability of a major flood event could be statistically low; however, for a civil protection official who carries ultimate legal and operational responsibility, that 1% carries a significantly larger weight. The forecasting framework must bridge this gap, ensuring that uncertainty is translated into a clear baseline that supports the person in charge.

Furthermore, the implementation of the statistical post-processing framework can offer a scientific validation of the operator's intuition by confirming recurring operational observations, such as systematic flow over- or under-estimations for specific regions. This backing provides critical justification when operators must make the difficult decision to manually lower or adjust automated alert thresholds to prevent unnecessary false alarms.

Ultimately, managing and communicating uncertainty cannot be treated as a static, one-time setup. It is an iterative process. Operational protocols and water resources management strategies must continuously evolve as we learn from subsequent hydro-climatic events and real-world decisions. Building long-term technical trust and robust collaborative formats requires cross-sector collaborations, targeted workshops, post-event reviews and continuous feedback loops (see, e.g., the attached technical meeting slides).

4.4 Future implementations

To target any improvements in high- and low-flow prediction, the incorporation of loss functions tailored specifically to extremes into the semi-parametric hydrological post-processing framework for predictive uncertainty estimation is planned, following recent research efforts by Papacharalampous et al. (2026). Additionally, a real-time, operational forecasting framework combining concepts from both the current system and the post-processing framework is planned. This integration is intended to simultaneously facilitate bias correction and provide reliable uncertainty estimates in real time, while translating these into actionable operational insights.

Acknowledgements: The present study was developed in the framework of the ATLAS project, with financial support provided by the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen, Italy.

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